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DESIGN OF CHALLENGE BASED EDUCATION: EXPERIENCES WITH INTRODUCING CBE IN THE ECIU UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

Background

With new knowledge developing at an ever higher speed and problems crossing boundaries more and more (both disciplinary as well as nationally), future graduates need to be able to solve multidimensional problems in at least multidisciplinary teams while adjusting to this continuous and rapid change.

Many parties already call for a change in engineering education, for more interdisciplinarity, with more individual learning paths, greater focus on 21st century skills and more learning skills (Goldberg & Sommerville, 2014; Graham 2018; OECD 2018; Elearning industry), which stimulates students to develop adaptive expertise (Taylor, 2007; Bohle Carbonell, 2014). Challenge Based Education is an educational approach that can help engineering students develop these competencies (Taylor, 2007; CBL).

In line with their motto (and ambition) to challenge conventional thinking about education and in response to the EU call for creating European Universities (EU, 2017), the European Consortium of Innovative Universities (ECIU) founded the "ECIU University". Core of the ECIU University is Challenge Based Education (CBE).

CBE is a learner centered approach that gives opportunity to individual learning outcomes. It brings together learners, faculty, and stakeholders from across society to work on relevant global challenges, while at the same time aiming to find a solution which is environmentally, socially and economically sustainable and has real, local impact (Kohn Rådberg et al. 2020, p 22). Multidisciplinary teams of learners work together to follow three different phases: *Engage, Investigate, Act* to solve the challenge (CBL).

During the *Engage* phase, the team starts with the Big Idea, the challenge that is relevant for the individual learner and society. Based on this, the team defines Essential Questions, important problems that follow from the Big Idea. Elaborating on

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these Essential Questions, the team decides on an actionable Challenge Statement, the problem they will be working on.

During the second phase, *Investigate*, the team starts with Guiding Questions to find out what they need to learn about the challenge statement in order to come up with a plan how to find an appropriate solution. During the Guiding Activities the team finds new sources and learns more about the topic. During Synthesis the team combines all newly acquired information.

In the final *Act* phase, the team starts with Solution Concepts, different ideas to solve the problem. In the Solution Development they develop the solution they think will work best. Implementation and Evaluation then follows where the team actually implements the solution, evaluates its working and if necessary improves upon it. Important to notice is that throughout the whole process, the team members continuously document and share their experiences, and reflect on their own actions and learning. It is crucial, that the last step of a CBE-project is reflection on the learning and working process.

LEARNING OBJECTIVES OF THE WORKSHOP

In this workshop, the participants will learn how the different phases of CBE are done, by working on a challenge themselves. As the challenge is about introducing CBE in a university, they will also learn about what is needed to implement CBE in their own programme. Examples and resources will be available, so the participants will learn from these as well.

SET UP OF THE WORKSHOP

At the start of the workshop, participants will discuss the challenge given to define the essential questions. They will then be divided into small multidisciplinary groups, to further elaborate on different actionable challenge statements. In the small groups they will go through the different phases of CBE, and will receive support when necessary. At the end all subgroups will share their ideas with the whole group which will be summarized, so every participant will have a complete overview of ideas on how to introduce CBE.

To make the workshop interesting for all participants, we would like to have between 12 and 30 participants.

EVALUATION OF LEARNING RESULTS

After the presentations of the subgroups, the participants will reflect on their own experience, write down their lessons learned and additional questions. We'll ask several participants to share their experiences.

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